

STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY OF DISCONTINUOUS BLADE STIFFENED BRAIDED AND WOVEN COMPOSITE PANELS

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SUMMARY: The objective of this study was to evaluate the structural integrity of discontinuous blade stiffened panels made of textile preform composites and compare the failure stresses and modes with that of conventional laminated stiffened panels. Three-dimensional braided and 3-D orthogonal woven composite panels were evaluated. Panels were made of BASF G30-500 graphite fiber yarns and Dow Chemicals Tactix-123 matrix. Panels were consolidated by resin transfer molding. The panel configuration was similar to that used in a previous FAA contract. Three-dimensional finite-element analysis was used to establish the geometrical configuration and identify the regions of high stresses. Test results showed that fracture in both braided and woven panels was by net section tensile failure. Notch root stress (strain) concentration causes failure initiation but its influence on the ultimate strength was minimal. Failure initiation in braided panel was by peeling and in woven panel it was by shear.

KEYWORDS: blade stiffened panel, braided composites, woven composites, tension load, structural integrity, resin transfer molding, 3-D finite-element analysis, stress concentration

INTRODUCTION

Advances made in laminated polymeric composites have proved that they are stronger, stiffer, and lighter than conventional metallic materials for number of applications, including aerospace structures, sports equipment and transport structures. The current emphasis on affordability of composite structures is driving material scientists and manufacturing technologists to focus on the use of low cost materials and manufacturing techniques. Textile fabric preforms and resin transfer molding (RTM) lend themselves to manufacture near net shape components. The RTM process uses cheaper dry preform and matrix instead of expensive prepregs. Hence, it is found to be a viable low cost manufacturing technique for structural components.

Figure 1.- Northrop-Grumman test specimen

A number of studies are being made in government agencies, industries, and universities to evaluate the engineering properties and structural integrity of textile composites. The objective of this paper is to evaluate the structural integrity of discontinuous blade stiffened 3-D braided and woven composite panels. Both analytical as well as experimental techniques were used for this purpose. Northrop-Grumman Corp. under a FAA contract investigated the structural integrity of discontinuous blade stiffener in laminated composite panel (see Fig. 1) [1]. The present study is focused on integrally braided and woven composite panels. In such panels, problems associated with laminated composites no longer exists, but there may be other problems related to the fiber architecture. Both 3-D finite-element analysis and experiments are conducted and the results are compared with each other and with the results of Northrop-Grumman test data.

TEST PANEL AND MATERIAL SYSTEM

In an earlier study Northrop-Grumman Corporation examined the structural integrity of discontinuous blade stiffened laminated composite panel (see Fig. 1), fabricated from unidirectional composite laminae. The purpose of that study was to establish a certification procedure for terminating stiffeners used in selected sections in transport aircraft wings. In the present study the focus is on the evaluation of the structural integrity of integrally constructed textile preform composite panels. These panels were made of BASF's G30-500 graphite fibers and Dow Chemicals Tactix 123 matrix. Integral braiding and weaving technology was used in manufacturing the panels with stiffeners. Fabric architecture of the braid is designated by $(0/\pm 17^\circ)$ with 46% axials, whereas the 3-D orthogonal woven fabric architecture is $(0/90/90)$ with 50% axials. The average fiber volume fractions of braided and woven composites were 0.38 and 0.44 [2], respectively. Originally, the preform fabrics were manufactured to have two-blade stiffeners and were resin transfer molded into two blade stiffened panels.

Figure 2: NCA&TSU test specimen

Table 1: In-situ Properties of stiffened Panels

Property	Braided Panel B3a GPa (Msi)	Woven Panel W3b GPa (Msi)
E_x	67.8 (9.8)	77.9 (10.9)
E_y^*	33.9 (4.9)	37.4 (5.4)
E_z^*	33.9 (4.9)	37.4 (5.4)
G_{xy}	5.5 (0.8)	2.8 (0.4)
G_{yz}^*	2.1 (0.3)	2.1 (0.3)
G_{xz}^*	5.5 (0.8)	2.8 (0.4)
ν_{xy}	0.77	0.06
ν_{yz}^*	0.05	0.05
ν_{xz}^*	0.77	0.05

* Assumed Properties

The nominal dimensions of the panel were: length = 457 mm, width = 165 mm, thickness = 6.1 mm, blade depth = 19 mm, and spacing between blades = 89 mm. From each of these resin transfer molded panels, two single blade stiffened panel specimens as well as other specimens required for in-situ mechanical property evaluation were obtained. Figure 2 shows the geometric configuration of the panel in terms of geometric parameters. A detailed finite element study [3] was conducted to establish these geometric parameters. The criteria used were: Constant strain should be present over a minimum length of 50 mm in both unnotched and notched sections of the panel, and the highest strain concentration should occur at the notch root. The grip length was designed based on the load required to fracture the panel using friction grips. The geometry of the test specimens finally chosen for the discontinuous blade stiffened panel specimen is shown in Fig. 2.

In-situ Properties

The ends of the panel were tabbed using 8 mm (5/16") thick cross-ply glass/epoxy tabs. This tab thickness was chosen based on the stiffener height at the grip end. In-situ properties of braided and woven panels were measured for simulating the panel test response by finite element analysis. Tension, compression, and Iosipescu shear specimens were extracted from the stiffened panels. These specimens were tested using procedures similar to the ASTM test procedures [4, 5] to obtain E_z , ν_{xy} , and G_{xy} . At least 3 specimens were tested for each of the above properties. Table 1 lists the average values of the different properties measured along with some of the assumed properties which are indicated by the superscript '*' in the table.

Fig. 3: Finite-element model of one-quarter of the specimen.

Fig. 4: Deformed shape of the finite-element model.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF TEST PANELS

Finite Element Model

A finite element model of one-quarter of the test panel is shown in Fig. 3. This model had 2575, 20-node isoparametric solid element and 12,740 nodes. Symmetric boundary conditions were imposed on $z = 0$ and $x = l/2$ planes. A uniform displacement u_x was imposed on the specimen at $x = 0$. The displacement corresponding to an average axial strain of 1% was imposed. To simulate gripping conditions, additional rigid body displacement in y -direction was imposed at $x = y = z = 0$. Because the friction grips does not allow the tabbed length of the specimen to rotate, an equivalent condition was simulated by restraining y -direction displacement of the tabs.

A preliminary calculation showed that the tab deformation due to friction induced load in y -direction was about 0.05 mm (0.002 in.). Therefore one-half of this displacement was imposed on top and bottom tab surfaces. The material properties given in Table 1 were used for both flange and stiffener of the panel. A linear elastic analysis [6] was conducted and the displacements, strains, and stresses were calculated at the nodes.

Finite-Element Results

Figure 4 shows a typical deformed shape of the finite-element model. Note that the deformation of the 2nd half of the model is added to get a total view of the panel deformation. The deformed shape indicate that: (1) Maximum strain occurs at top surface in the mid section of the panel and (2) Concentration of stiffener peeling (σ_y) and shear (τ_{xy}) stresses is present at the notch root of the stiffener. Figures 5 and 6 show the distribution of σ_y and τ_{xy} ahead (towards the unnotched section) of the notch for both braided and woven panels. All stresses are normalized by the average applied stress at the gripped ends. High stresses are limited to a distance of 25 mm from the notch root. Although the notch stress concentration varies from 30% to 40% of the average σ_x stress, they are high enough to cause peeling and/or shearing of the stiffener. Orthogonal weaves are weak in shear, therefore, the failure can initiate as shearing failure. Braided composites are strong in shear but not in peeling (a matrix dominant direction). Because of interlocking of fiber yarns, failure initiation by peeling would be suppressed. More details of the stress analysis are given in Ref. 3.

Fig. 5: σ_y distribution away from the notch.

Fig. 6: τ_{xy} distribution away from the notch.

STIFFENED PANEL TESTS

Instrumentation and test procedure

The panel specimens were instrumented with strain gages at selected locations as shown in Fig. 7. Strain gages with 12.3 mm x 4.6 mm active grid were used. The strain gage readings as well as load levels and displacements from the test machine were recorded using a 20 channel strain gage data acquisition system. In addition, the corners between the stiffener and flange, where high peel and shear strains are expected, were coated with a thin uniform layer of typewriter correction fluid. This layer served in a manner similar to brittle coating, indicating regions of severe strains. Failure initiation in these regions were monitored during the tests. Panels were tested in an MTS 810 test machine, under load control, at the rate of 22.24 KN/min. until failure.

Fig. 7: Strain gage locations.

Test Results

The load displacement curves for the braided and woven panels are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. The load-displacement response is initially linear and then it becomes nonlinear (softening). The softening was due to a number of microscopic failures initiating and progressing in the specimens.

Most of the braided specimens showed first failure around the notch root of the stiffener. As the load increased, the number of cracks increased both at the notch root and all along the notch section. Finally specimens failed as net section tensile failure.

In the woven panels the failure initiated as shear failure at the notch root and then leading to shearing of the stiffener. The final fracture was by the net section tensile failure of the panel. Three of the five panels fractured and the strength of remaining two exceeded the machine capacity. Table 2 lists the fracture load and the fracture stress (based on the cross-sectional area at the notch section) of all the tested panels. The average fracture stress of the barided and woven panels were 433.7 and 501.9 MPa, respectively. Data scatter was less than 2% for

woven panels and it was +17%/-15% for braided panels. In conclusion, fracture in both braided and woven panels was by net section tensile failure. Notch root stress (strain) concentration causes failure initiation but its influence on the ultimate strength is minimal. Failure initiation in braided panel is by peeling and in woven panel it is by shear.

Fig 8: Load-elongation response of braided composite panels.

<i>Table 2: Panel test results</i>			
Specimen No	Area of cross-section @ mm ²	Failure load KN	Fracture Strength MPa
<u>Braided composite panels:</u>			
B1B	362.1	133.4	368.5
B3A	322.2	163.7	508.1
B3B	319.3	154.8	484.8
BT0	359.7	133.4	370.8
BT1	411.5	179.6	436.5
<u>Woven composite panels</u>			
W2A*	333.4	-	-
W3B	320.5	160.1	499.6
W2B*	328.8	-	-
WT0	324.9	165.7	510.1
WT1	354.5	175.8	496.1

* Load exceeded test machine's capacity

Figure 10 shows load versus strain response at selected locations in the braided panel. The locations at the mid-section of the stiffener (S_{g3} and S_{g11}, the strain gages at the top and bottom surfaces), mid-section of the notch which was also the mid-section of the panel (S_{g5} and S_{g9}, the strain gages at the top and bottom surfaces), and the strain gage S_{g2}, on the stiffener. Refer to Fig. 7 for the description of the strain gage locations. The top and bottom strain gage pair indicate that the panel is subjected to both bending and membrane strains. The bending strain at the mid-section of the panel is large (difference between S_{g5} and S_{g9} is larger than the difference between S_{g3} and S_{g11}). Furthermore,

stiffener does carry some load (non-zero strain). But the stiffener strain values are less than 50% of the membrane strains. Note that the horizontal steps in the strain gage response are indicative of major failures in the specimen. Membrane and bending components of the strain at mid-section of the stiffener and the notch are shown in Figs. 11 and 12 respectively.

Membrane strains at these locations are almost identical for braided panel and the difference for the woven panels is less than 10%. Bending strains, as it can be inferred from the finite-element results (see Fig. 4) is larger at the mid-section of the panel (location 3) than at the mid-section of the stiffener (location 1). The bending strain at location 1 is almost half the bending strain at location 3 for braided composites. However, bending strain is much smaller (stabilized around $250 \mu\epsilon$) for woven composite panel. The difference in the two composites results may be due to difference in the material properties.

Fig 9: Load-elongation response of woven composite panels.

Fig. 10: Load-strain plot at selected strain gage locations for braided composite panel (B_{3a}).

Fig. 11: The membrane component of the strains at strain gage locations 1 and 3.

Fig. 12: The bending component of the strains at strain gage locations 1 and 3.

Fig. 13 shows comparison of strains S_{g1} and S_{g3} obtained from the finite-element analysis with the test data for the woven specimen. Broken lines through symbols represent the analysis and solid lines represent the test. Finite-element strains at S_{g1} agreed very well with test data, whereas the F-E strains at S_{g3} were larger than the test data; but the difference is less than 10% and may be due to local variations in the material properties.

Fig. 13: Comparison of F-E strain data with test for woven composite panel (W_{3b}).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The objective of this study was to evaluate the structural integrity of discontinuous blade stiffened panels made of textile preform composites and compare the failure stresses and modes with that of conventional laminated stiffened panels. Three-dimensional braided and 3-D orthogonal woven composite panels were evaluated. Panels were made of BASF G30-500 graphite fiber yarns and Dow Chemicals Tactix-123 matrix. Panels were consolidated by resin transfer molding. The panel configuration was similar to that was used in a previous FAA contract. Three-dimensional finite-element analysis was used to establish the geometrical configuration and identify the regions of high stresses. Peel and shear stress concentrations were found to be at the notch root and it was the site for failure initiation. Furthermore, the bending stress at the mid-section of the panel was larger than that at the stiffener section. Test results showed that fracture in both braided and woven panels was by net section tensile failure. Notch root stress (strain) concentration causes failure initiation but its influence on the ultimate strength was minimal. Failure initiation in braided panel was by peeling and in woven panel it was by shear. The average fracture stress of the braided and woven panels were 433.7 and 501.9 MPa, respectively. Strains calculated from the finite-element analysis generally agreed with the test data.

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